

TWO NEW SPECIES OF *ALVANIA* (RISSOIDAE) FROM THE AZORES

Serge Gofas*

The following descriptions are intended for naming two undescribed species of *Alvania* from the Azores, as a preliminary to a survey of azorian Rissoidae (GOFAS, in press). This work has been completed during the first international workshop on Malacology (Vila Franca do Campo, São Miguel, July 1988) organized by University of Azores under supervision of Pr. A. FRIAS MARTINS.

Holotypes and most material examined are deposited in Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris. Paratypes and relevant material are also in the collection of University of Azores, and of Instituto de Investigação Científica Tropical (Centro de Zoologia), Lisbon.

Alvania mediolittoralis n. sp.

(fig. 1-4; 15)

Type locality: Ponta da Galera, São Miguel, Azores (intertidal zone).

Type material: Holotype and numerous paratypes from the type locality (BOUCHET, HEROS AND METIVIER coll., 1983).

Other material examined: (numerous specimens unless otherwise stated).

São Miguel: Caloura 4 m, 2 sh.; Vila Franca 24 m, 9 sh. ("Biaçores", 1971). Ponta da Galera, intertidal; Ponta Delgada, 22 sh.; Capelas, intertidal (BOUCHET, HEROS, METIVIER coll. 1983). Agua d'Alto, intertidal (workshop, 7/1988).

Faial: Horta 7 m, 1 shell ("Biaçores", 1971).

Description: Dimensions of adult shell $2 \times 1,1$ mm to $2,7 \times 1,5$ mm. Protoconch $1 \frac{1}{4}$ clearly demarcated whorl, rounded with 4-5 strong spiral lirae (fig. 4). Teleoconch $3 \frac{1}{4}$ to $3 \frac{1}{2}$ whorls, with tight sculpture of spiral beaded cords and axial folds. There are two spiral cords on the first postlarval whorl, then two more are intercalated and one cord adapically next to the suture is more strongly developed. The body whorl has about nine tightly and evenly spaced cords, slightly broader than inter-space; one of the cords touches the suture. The cords are distinctly beaded at intersection with tightly spaced axial folds, except on the anterior part of body whorl where the axials disappear. They bear a minute microsculpture of spirally aligned granules (fig. 15).

* Elf Aquitaine, 64018 Pau, and Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France.

Aperture thickened by a rim not clearly separated from the whorl, over which the spirals are faintly continued and tend to divide. Inside of aperture piriform, whit 5-6 very faint denticles.

Shell colour usually pale brown, grading to white on the apertural rim. Cords are commonly darker than the background, and there is also a darker stain next to the apertural rim. Some specimens show spiral banding; a few are very pale.

Remarks: DAUTZENBERG (1889: 49) has referred this species to *Alvania mariae* (d'Orbigny), a fossil species of the miocene Aquitaine basin. Recent specimens assigned to *A. mariae* were later assigned by DAUTZENBERG to *A. geryonia* (Chereghini) and are closely related to *A. beanii* (Hanley, 1844). These species from the mainland are grossly similar in shape but differ by larger size, protoconch whit two quite smooth whorls and tiny apex (indicating planktotrophic development) and a larger number of spiral cords. They are not very closely related to the azorian species considered here.

A. mediolittoralis resembles *A. leacocki* (Watson, 1873) of Madeira. I have examined WATSON'S syntypes and found them to contain two different morphs; all of them differ from the azorian species in having three beaded spirals on the whorls instead of four. The specimen (fig. 5-6) selected as lectotype of *A. leacocki* by MOOLENBEECK (1988, unpublished?) has tightly packed rounded beads and broad coloured bands covering two or more cords. The other morph, maybe an additional species, has a clathrate sculpture and spirals strongly indenting the varix as in *A. cancellata* (da Costa, 1778).

Alvania mediolittoralis also resembles *Alvania manzonii* (Nordsieck, 1972), of the Canary Islands. NORDSIECK (1972: 184) introduced the name *Turbona calathus manzonii* with explicit reference to the specimen figured by MANZONI (1868) as *Rissoa calathus*. This specimen is presently in Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, and is here designated as the lectotype of *Alvania manzonii*. The canarian species (fig. 7-8) differs only by slightly larger size, paler shell on the average and a characteristically twisted and prominent nuclear whorl of the protoconch (fig. 8). It is not likely to be conspecific, considering the existence of quite different species in the intermediate sites of Madeira and Santa Maria.

Alvania formicarum n. sp.

(fig. 9-14)

Type locality: East coast of Formigas, Azores (depth 43 m).

Type material: Holotype and 11 paratypes from the type locality.

Other material examined: Ilheu S. Lourenço, Santa Maria (15 m), 1 shell.

Description: Dimensions of adult shell 2,4 × 1,4 mm. Protoconch 1 ¼ clearly demarcated whorl, rounded with 4-5 strong spiral lirae (Fig. 12-13).

Teleoconch 3 ¼ to 3 ¼ whorls, with strong sculpture of spiral beaded cords and axial folds. There are two spiral cords on the first postlarval whorl, then a third

one is added abapically along the suture. The body whorl has seven spiral cords, about as thick as the interspace; one of them is running quite close to the suture. Four cords are distinctly beaded at intersection with axial folds, whereas on the anterior part of body whorl the axials disappear. The cords bear a minute microsculpture of spirally aligned granules (fig. 14).

Aperture thickened by a rim not clearly separated from the whorl, over which the spirals are faintly continued and tend to divide. Inside of aperture pyriform, with 5-6 denticles.

Shell colour tawny with the beads paler and the cords darker between the beads.

Specimens collected in Formigas and Santa Maria by "Biaçores" leg of the "Jean-Charcot" represent an additional species. They have three beaded cords on the spire like *A. leacocki*, but differ in having a shorter spire, and an articulated colour pattern on the cords (whereas *A. leacocki* usually has broad brown bands running over two cords). They differ from *A. mediolittoralis* n. sp. by the coarse sculpture with three cords on spire whorls, and also by stouter outline and different colour pattern.

This species has not been found on the island of São Miguel, despite representative sampling at all depths down to 50 m. This observation denotes a poor capacity for dispersal and suggests that similar species from Madeira and Canary Islands are actually different species belonging to the same radiation.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author is grateful to Professor A. FRIAS MARTINS and to the University of Azores, for invitation to participate in the international workshop on Malacology, July 1988, and for funding therefore. Thanks are expressed to Dr. P. BOUCHET (Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris) for taking the SEM pictures, and to P. LOZOUET for presenting fossil material of *Alvania mariae*.

SUMMARY

Two new species of *Alvania* from the Azores are described; they are compared to *A. leacocki* Watson from Madeira and to a species from the Canary islands. A lectotype is designated for *Alvania manzonii* (Nordsieck, 1972).

RESUMO

Duas novas espécies de *Alvania* dos Açores são descritas; são comparadas com a *A. leacocki* Watson da Madeira e com uma espécie das Canárias. Um lectotipo é designado para *Alvania manzonii* (Nordsieck, 1972).

REFERENCES

- DAUTZENBERG P. (1989) — Contribution à la faune malacologique des Açores — *Res. Camp. Scient. Prince de Monaco*, 1: 112 p. 4 pl.
- GOFAS S. (in press) — The Rissoacean fauna of Azores. Açoreana, special issue of proceedings of the international workshop on Malacology.
- JEFFREYS J. G. (1987) — Description of a new species of Rissoa from Madeira — *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.* (3) 19: 435.
- MANZONI A. (1868) — Nouvelles especes de Rissoa recueillies aux îles Canaries et à Madère, par M. Mac-Andrew en 1852. — *J. Conchyl.* 16: 164-168.
- MANZONI A. (1868) — Sur les Rissoa des îles Canaries et de Madère recueillis par M. Mac-Andrew en 1852. — *J. Conchyl.* 16: 236-256.
- NORDSIECK F. (1972) — *Die europäischen Meeresschnecken (Opisthobranchia mit Pyramidellidae; Rissoacea)*. 327 p., 41 pl. Stuttgart, Gustav Fischer.
- WATSON R. B. (1873) — On some marine Mollusca from Madeira, including a new genus of the Muricidae, a new Eulima, and the whole of the Rissoae of the group of islands *Proc. Zool. Soc. London*: 361-391.
- WATSON R. B. (1886) — Report on the Scaphopoda and Gasteropoda — *Rep. sc. res. voy. H.M.S. Challenger 1873-76, zoology* 15, 756 p, 53 pl.

Fig. 1-4: *Alvania mediolittoralis* n. sp., Ponta da Galera

Fig. 1: Holotype (2,2 × 1,1 mm)

Fig. 2: Paratype (2,2 × 1,2 mm)

Fig. 3: Paratype (2,3 × 1,2 mm)

Fig. 4: Protoconch of another specimen.

Fig. 5-6: *Alvania leacocki* (Watson, 1873): Lectotype (BMNH 1875.5.27.3) (2,8 × 1,5 mm). Light photographs.

Fig. 7-8: *Alvania manzonii* (Nordsieck, 1972). San Andrés, Tenerife (2,35 × 1,4 mm) and protoconch of the same specimen.

1

2

3

4

8

100µm

100µm

5

6

7

Fig. 9-14: *Alvania formicarum* n. sp., Formigas

Fig. 9: Holotype (2,35 × 1,4 mm)

Fig. 10, 11: Paratypes (2,35 × 1,4 mm)

Fig. 12: Protoconch of specimen fig. 10

Fig. 13: Protoconch of specimen fig. 11

Fig. 14: Microsculpture of specimen fig. 10, × 270

Fig. 15: *Alvania mediolittoralis* n. sp. Microsculpture of specimen fig. 2, × 300

100µm

100µm

